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ISC 2025

XX INTERNATIONAL SILAGE CONFERENCE

JULY 21-24, 2025 | GAINESVILLE, FL USA

CONFERENCE PROGRAM BOOK

HOST ORGANIZATIONS

GLOBAL FOOD
SYSTEMS INSTITUTE

ANIMAL
SCIENCES

UF | IFAS
UNIVERSITY of FLORIDA

UF/IFAS AGRONOMY
DEPARTMENT

FORAGE TEAM

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Name Badge

Your name badge is your entry pass to all networking events at ISC 2025, so please wear it throughout the conference. As a reminder, due to spacing constraints, *guests are not permitted*.

AGENDA-AT-A-GLANCE

Sunday, July 20, 2025	
3:30pm–6:30pm	Registration Opens Exhibitor Move-In Poster Installation
4:30pm–5:30pm	Planning Committee Meeting
5:30pm–6:30pm	Welcome Social
Monday, July 21, 2025	
7:30am–5:00pm	Registration Opens
7:30am–8:30am	Morning Refreshments
7:30am–8:30am	Poster Installation
8:30am–11:30am	Plenary Session
11:30am–1:00pm	Group Lunch & Presentation
1:00pm–2:00pm	Formal Poster Viewing - Session 1
2:00pm–5:00pm	Plenary Session
5:00pm–6:00pm	Networking Social & Formal Poster Viewing - Session 1
6:00pm–7:30pm	Dinner Banquet
Tuesday, July 22, 2025	
7:30am–5:00pm	Registration Opens
7:30am–8:30am	Morning Refreshments
8:30am–11:30am	Concurrent Sessions
11:30am–1:00pm	Group Lunch
1:00pm–2:00pm	Formal Poster Viewing - Session 2
2:00pm–5:00pm	Concurrent Sessions
5:00pm–6:00pm	Networking Social & Formal Poster Viewing - Session 2
Wednesday, July 23, 2025	
7:30am–5:00pm	Registration Opens
7:30am–8:30am	Morning Refreshments
8:30am–11:30am	Concurrent Sessions
11:30am–12:30pm	Formal Poster Viewing - Session 3
12:30pm–2:00pm	Group Lunch, Presentation, & Awards
2:00pm–3:15pm	Plenary Session
3:15pm–4:15pm	Formal Poster Viewing - Session 3
4:15pm–5:00pm	Closing Plenary Session
5:00pm	Conference Concludes
Thursday, July 24, 2025	
7:30am–5:30pm	Optional Off-property Field Tour

POSTER DIRECTORY

(Posters are listed in order by topic, poster session, then by presenter last name.)

POSTER VIEWING 1

POSTER VIEWING 2

POSTER VIEWING 3

Advancing Silage Production for Small Holders						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
1	Muhammad	Shaheryar	Bahauddin Zakariya University	Pakistan	Ensuring Quality Feed Through Silage-Making for Smallholders	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
2	Olabode	Olanrewaju	Calvary Ministries CAPRO	Nigeria	Silage, A Potential Solution to the Farmer-Herder Conflicts that Have Killed Tens of Thousands in West Africa- A Missionary's Perspective	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
3	Nouhoun	Zampaligre	Centre National de Recherche Scientifique et Technologique (CNRST)	Burkina Faso	Small Scale Corn Silage for Quality Fodder Conservation in the Integrated Crop-Livestock Systems of the Sahel	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
Aerobic Stability						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
5	Angelika	Borkowska	Volac International Ltd	United Kingdom	Amino Acids in Lucerne Silage: 2. Effects of Inoculation	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
7	Kristin	Rang	University of Bonn	Germany	Impact of Ensiling and Storage Temperature on the Aerobic Stability of Maize Silage	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
10	Hana	Synkova	NutriVet s.r.o.	Czech Republic	Monitoring Changes in Temperature of Fermented Feeds and Their Aerobic Stability	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
4	Mukti	Bhandari	University of Delaware	United States	Effect of Inoculant on Alfalfa Silage Challenged with Air Stress and Loosely Packed Conditions	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
8	Thiago	da Silva	Universidade Federal Rural da Amazônia	Brazil	Aerobic Deterioration of Diets Containing Cassava Shoot and Root Silages	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
6	Shane	Cronin	IFF Nutrition and Biosciences	United States	Effect of Laboratory Bag Silo Plastic Type on Fermentation of Corn Silage	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
9	Joao	Daniel	State University of Maringa	Brazil	Obligate Heterofermentative Lactic Acid Bacteria Decrease Losses During Storage and Feedout in Corn Silage Fermented for Long Period	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
Baleage and Other Silages						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
16	Joos	Latré	University of Applied Sciences and Arts	Belgium	Ensiling Moist Cereal-Legume Intercrops: A Promising Conservation Technique, Reducing Anti-Nutritional Factors in Faba Beans	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
11	Daniel Jose	Cavalli Vieira	University of Wisconsin-Madison	United States	Survey of Fiber Quality of Cover Crops Used as Forage to Dairy Cattle in Wisconsin	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
14	Ivan	Eisner	Novonesis	Denmark	Improving the Quality of Haylage for Horses by Adding a Biological Silage Additive	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
17	Anibal Coutinho	Rego	Federal University of Ceara	Brazil	Dry Matter Concentration Affects the Relationships with Variables Linked to Cassava Haylage Characteristics	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22

Silage Additives (continued)						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
81	Paulina	Pogorzelska-Przybyłek	University of Warmia and Mazury	Poland	Chemical Composition and in Vitro Rumen Degradability of Crude Protein in Whole Crop Hemp Silages	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
85	Karina	Ribeiro	Universidade Federal de Viçosa	Brazil	Effect of Microbial Inoculation and Regrowth Age on Ruminal Degradation Kinetics of Arachis Pintoil Silage	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
88	Edson	Santos	Federal University of Paraíba	Brazil	Bacterial Diversity of Forage Sorghum Silage Treated with <i>Lentilactobacillus Buchneri</i> or Organic Acids	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
93	Elisabeth	Weidenholzer	Lactosan GmbH & Co. KG	Austria	Effect of a Silage Inoculant on Fermentation Quality and Biogas Yield of Different Grass Silage Varieties	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
96	Jie	Zhao	Nanjing Agricultural University	China	Effects of Enzymes, Microbiota and Organic Acids on Structural Carbohydrate During Ensiling of Sudan Grass	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
Tropical Silages						
#	First Name	Last Name	Organization	Country	Abstract Title	Poster Session
100	Janaina	Bragatto	State University of Maringa	Brazil	Assessment of the Fermentative Profile of Tropical Grass Silages on Brazilian Beef Farms	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
103	Matheus G.M.	Carvalho	University of New Hampshire	United States	Effect of Replacing Hexamine by Sodium Formate in Nitrite-Based Additives for Palisade Grass Silage	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
106	Juliana	Oliveira	Federal University of Paraíba	Brazil	Bacterial Dynamics in Mixtures Based on Forage Cactus and Sorghum Silage During Aerobic Exposure	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
109	Diwakar	Vyas	Department of Animal Sciences	United States	Effects of Microbial Inoculation on Silage Fermentation and Preservation Characteristics of Cool-Season Grass-Legume Mixtures in Southeastern Dairy Systems	Poster Viewing 1: Mon, July 21
98	Tomilola	Arilekolasi	Federal University Oye-Ekiti	Nigeria	Impact of Ensiling on Nutritive Quality and Methane Emission from Molasses-Treated <i>Gmelina Arborea</i> Leaves for Sustainable Ruminant-Production	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
101	Janaina	Bragatto	State University of Maringa	Brazil	Effect of Combinations of Lactic Acid Bacteria on the Fermentation of Sugarcane Silage	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
107	Juliana	Oliveira	Federal University of Paraíba	Brazil	Contamination on the <i>Escherichia Coli</i> in Total Mixed Rations with High Proportions of Forage Cactus	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
110	Maity	Zopollatto	Federal University of Parana	Brazil	Chemical Composition of King Grass Silages with Inclusion of <i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	Poster Viewing 2: Tues, July 22
99	Musibau	Bamikole	University of Benin	Nigeria	Potential of Citrus Sinensis Peels Inclusion on the Nutritive Quality of <i>Megathyrus maximus</i> Silage	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
102	Peter	Dele	Federal University of Agriculture	Nigeria	Mineral Contents of Sweet Corn Stover Silage: Effect of Mechanical Processing and Ensiling Duration	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
105	Luiz Gustavo	Nussio	University of São Paulo	Brazil	Associative Effect of Ingredient Sources on the Partial Mixed Ration and TMR Silages Based on WDBS for Feedlot Beef Cattle Diets in Brazil	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23
108	Anibal Coutinho	Rego	Federal University of Ceara	Brazil	Sheep Feed Preference for the Aerial Part of Cassava Preserved by Different Methods	Poster Viewing 3: Wed, July 23